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**MUSEALISATION OF GENOCIDE AND CRIMES AGAINST HUMANITY
IN THE CONTEXT OF EUROPEAN MEMORY CULTURE**

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**МУЗЕАЛІЗАЦІЯ ГЕНОЦИДУ ТА ЗЛОЧИНІВ ПРОТИ ЛЮДСТВА
В КОНТЕКСТІ ЄВРОПЕЙСЬКОЇ КУЛЬТУРИ ПАМ'ЯТІ**

Memorial museums are influential institutions of culture memory, a common trend is the orientation towards the moral imperative of respect for human rights. They based on the “universalization of the Holocaust” in order to prevent new atrocities and human suffering. Memorial museums are designed to both inform the public about a specific historical event associated with mass suffering and to perpetuate its memory. According to the International Memorial Museums Charter, memorial museums have a responsibility to protect the dignity of victims from all forms of exploitation and to ensure, in addition to traditional history lessons, that the interpretation of historical events encourages critical reflection on the past. Memorial museums are a relatively new phenomenon, as their focus on the most painful aspects of the past reflects efforts to engage critically with past violence. They also remind visitors that, despite ethnic and national differences, the pursuit of justice, freedom, dignity, and respect is central to human existence.

The United States Holocaust Memorial Museum (USHMM) is considered a certain model for imitation in the creation of memorial forms to perpetuate the stories of genocide and crimes against humanity. The museum was opened in 1993, and work on its creation had been ongoing since 1978, when, at the initiative of then-US President Jimmy Carter, the Presidential Commission on the Holocaust (later renamed the United States Holocaust Memorial Council) was established. As is known, this initiative sparked a wide debate about the concept of the museum, which was prompted by the commissioning of a project for a national memorial to the “six million killed in the Holocaust”. Representatives of various non-Jewish groups of victims of Nazism later demanded similar victim status and inclusion in the museum concept. The definition of the Holocaust was therefore expanded (in 1979) to include “eleven million innocent victims, of whom six million were Jewish”. In contrast, Elie Wiesel, who at the time chaired the Holocaust Memorial Commission, emphasized the unique and exclusive goal of the Nazi regime — the extermination of all Jews; later summing up this with the oft-quoted phrase: “Not all victims were Jews, but all Jews were victims”. The USHMM now uses the term “Holocaust” as a synonym for the

Nazi extermination of Jews; the systematic, state-organized persecution and murder of six million European Jews by the Nazi German regime and its allies and collaborators. It is also noted that in addition to committing the Holocaust, Nazi Germany also persecuted and murdered millions of other victims, other groups of people considered enemies or a threat — civilians (non-Jews) accused of disobedience, resistance or partisan activity; people with disabilities; Roma, Soviet prisoners of war, etc.

The experts note that there is currently a certain contradiction between the identity of the Holocaust as a unique, catastrophic event against the Jewish people (Shoah) and its continued use as a universal model for understanding the suffering of others. Holocaust remembrance was especially in the early 2000s since as a crucial for building an international consensus on human rights.

The Holocaust is also central to the EU's policy on the culture of remembrance of the Second World War. For Europe as a whole, the Holocaust is also conveyed as a symbol of the dangers of aggressive nationalism and xenophobia, the rejection of democratic values and the violation of human rights. (Western) European memorial models of commemorating the victims of Nazism encourage visitors to the memorials to have a humanistic perception of genocides and mass atrocities. The information conveyed by the exhibitions should evoke sympathy for the victims — for the specific individuals and groups persecuted by the Nazi regime. The recognition of the Holocaust in common European history has become an informal condition for accession to the EU, especially for the 2004 Eastern enlargement of the EU.

Although the memory of the Holocaust has become a negative founding myth in Europe, there are differences and competing politics of memory between the “West” and the “East” of Europe. The Holocaust took place mainly in Eastern European countries and the extermination of mainly Eastern European Jews; and the scale of human suffering and human loss (non-Jewish) during World War II (as well as before and after) is also often assessed here as much greater than in Western European countries. Not all of this suffering and loss, especially at the hands of the Soviet authorities and local communists, is acknowledged in the West. This “memory split” between “East” and “West” has prompted representatives of post-communist states to demand that communist crimes be condemned in the same way as the Holocaust. Since in the countries of Central and Eastern Europe, not only Germany but also the Soviet Union is considered an aggressor, museums also present the crimes of the Soviet regime, often in the context of competing narratives of victimhood. For example, the narrative of the World War II Museum in Gdańsk, according to the curator of the permanent exhibition, Paweł Machcewicz, represents an East-Central European perspective on the Polish experience of war under two totalitarian regimes, the Nazi and the Soviet.

For Ukraine, which received official EU candidate status in June 2022, the “Europeanization of memory” of the museum discourse on World War II and the Holocaust has become particularly important. Ukrainian researchers and society are reflecting on various memorial discourses, somewhat similar to the Eastern European perspective of the “competition of victims” of Nazism and Communism in Eastern Europe. In addition, the Ukrainian debate includes the problematic issue of the “co-responsibility of the Soviet regime for the Holocaust”, since Stalin knew that the first victims of the Nazi occupation would be Jews, yet Soviet propaganda kept silent about the Nazi crimes against Jews (from 1939 to 1941) and nothing was done to evacuate them.

Several Holocaust memorialization projects have been implemented in Ukraine, initiated and implemented by Jewish communities (in Dnipro, Vinnytsia, Odesa, Kharkiv, Kryvyi Rih and other cities). The National Historical and Memorial Reserve “Babyn Yar” was established in Kyiv, but public debates over the concept of the museum have continued for many years. The debates were particularly heated between the museum concept developed by a working group at the Institute of Ukrainian History of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine and another, private initiative involving international experts and Russian investors. Ukrainian Holocaust researchers and museum experts cite a number of reasons for this situation: from the policy of Soviet forgetting to modern Russian influences, even during the ongoing Russian aggression in Ukraine; the “Russian project” has been widely criticized by the public for completely ignoring the non-Jewish victims of Babyn Yar, seeking to shift responsibility for the Holocaust onto Ukrainians, and glorifying the USSR, in particular as the savior of the Jews.

In time of the ongoing Russo-Ukrainian War, the National Historical and Memorial Reserve “Babyn Yar” provides exhibition space for temporary exhibitions that offer visitors a comparative perspective of the Holocaust with the crimes of the Soviet and Russian regimes: “Bakhmut — the Face of Genocide 1942/2022. A Retrospective of the Tragedy of World War II and Our Days”, “Babyn Yar: Mirrors of Death”, and others. Babyn Yar is not presented as an isolated event of the Holocaust, but through it an attempt is made to construct a complex multi-perspective of the space of totalitarian violence. The Ukrainian focus of the remembrance of Babyn Yar encompasses a larger time cycle of extreme violence, as well as makes a possible comparison through museum means of crimes committed by three regimes: Nazism, Communism and Rashism / Russian fascism.

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